

A Comparative Study on the Kinetics and Mechanism of Silver and Mercurous Ion Catalysed Aquation of Chloro and Bromo-(Ethylenediamine)-(Diethylenetriamine)Cobalt(III) Cations

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The kinetics of Ag^+ and Hg_2^{2+} assisted aquations of $[\text{Co}(\text{en})(\text{dien})\text{X}]^{2+}$ ($\text{X}=\text{Cl}, \text{Br}$; $\text{en}=\text{ethylenediamine}$, $\text{dien}=\text{diethylenetriamine}$) have been studied spectrophotometrically over a range of temp at constant pH and ionic strength. The kinetics obey the rate law

$$-\frac{d[\text{complex}]}{dt} = kK[\text{M}^{n+}]/(1 + K[\text{M}^{n+}])$$

$(\text{M}^{n+} = \text{Ag}^+, \text{Hg}_2^{2+})$

The reactions involve a bridged transition state. Activation parameters, the formation equilibrium constant of the adduct (K) and the first order rate constants for its dissociation (k) have been calculated. The rate of aquation of the bromo complex is faster than that of the chloro complex. On the basis of the results a mechanism of reaction is suggested.

ALTHOUGH aquation reactions of cobalt(III) complexes have been studied more extensively than any other octahedral substitution, it still is impossible to assign detailed mechanistic paths for them. It is well known that metal ions have a superiority over hydrogen ion in that they are themselves Lewis acids, usually have a positive charge greater than one, and can readily form metal chelates.

A large number of workers¹⁻⁷ have investigated the metal ion catalysed aquation of various cobalt(III) complexes by different techniques. The metal ions used are Ag^+ , Hg_2^{2+} , Tl^{3+} , Mn^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Al^{3+} , Ga^{3+} , In^{3+} and Fe^{3+} . Pearson *et al*⁸ studied the rate of acid hydrolysis of $[\text{Co}(\text{en})(\text{dien})\text{Cl}]\text{Cl}_2$ by a titrimetric technique. Many isomers of $[\text{Co}(\text{en})(\text{dien})\text{X}]^{2+}$ have been previously reported⁹⁻¹¹ and their aquation rates studied. Hg_2^{2+} catalysed aquations of the three isomers of $[\text{Co}(\text{en})(\text{dien})\text{Cl}]^{2+}$ have been studied¹² and it is found that the isomerisation between three chloro isomers plays no significant role in their hydrolysis reactions.

This communication reports the results of Ag^+ and Hg_2^{2+} assisted aquations of $[\text{Co}(\text{en})(\text{dien})\text{X}]_2\text{X}_2$ ($\text{X}=\text{Cl}, \text{Br}$). The investigations were undertaken to make a comparative study of the role of silver and mercurous ions as catalysts, with a view to exploring the underlying mechanism. The aim also was to get further insight into the nature of the leaving group on the rate of aquation.

Experimental

The ligands ethylenediamine and diethylenetriamine (supplied by Pfaltz and Bauer, Inc., U.S.A)

were distilled before use. Silver nitrate and mercurous nitrate (B.D.H. AnalaR) were used as catalysts. All other chemicals were of A.R. or G.R. grade. Double distilled water was used for making all the solutions. KNO_3 was used to maintain the ionic strength (μ). The preparation of the complexes is described elsewhere¹³.

Kinetics :

Spectrophotometric measurements were made with an Ecil spectrophotometer using 1 cm matched optical cell, distilled water being used as 100% transmission standard.

The requisite amounts of silver nitrate/mercurous nitrate and potassium nitrate in dilute nitric acid in a 250 ml reaction flask were allowed to equilibrate to the reaction temp. in a thermostat. A solution of the requisite amount of the complex in distilled water was also separately equilibrated to the reaction temperature. After thermal equilibrium, the solution of the complex was added quickly to the reaction flask. The mixture (total volume 50 ml) was shaken thoroughly and quickly filtered out into a separate flask placed inside the thermostat. Aliquots of the reaction mixture were withdrawn at suitable time intervals and each sample was quickly filtered again or centrifuged. The optical density of the clear filtered samples was measured at 520 nm (chloro complex) and at 540 nm (bromo complex). At these wave lengths the parent complexes are the major absorbing species. The change in absorbance with time was monitored continuously for 90-120 min and 5-6 hr later an "infinity" reading was recorded. The optical cell was washed with distilled water and acetone after each reading.

TABLE 1—FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANTS FOR THE AQUATION OF [Co(en)(dien)X]²⁺

Sl. No.	Complex	[Complex]	[H ⁺]	μ	Rate constants, k _{obs} × 10 ⁴ sec ⁻¹										Ref.
					Temp. °C										
					35	40	50	60	65	70	75	79.5	80	89	
1.	[Co(en)(dien)Cl]Cl ₂	0.025 M	0.1 M, HNO ₃	1.0	—	0.85	1.20	2.50	—	—	—	—	—	—	This work
2.	[Co(en)(dien)Br]Br ₂	0.025 M	0.1 M, HNO ₃	1.0	—	0.82	1.15	2.56	—	—	—	—	—	—	This work
3.	[Co(en)(dien)Cl] ²⁺	0.005 M	0.1 M, HNO ₃	—	0.05	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	8
4.	ω-[Co(en)(dien)Cl] ²⁺	—	0.01 M, HClO ₄	—	—	—	—	—	2.3	3.4	6.3	9.6	—	21	9
5.	ε-[Co(en)(dien)Cl] ²⁺	—	0.01 M, HClO ₄	—	—	—	—	—	5.0	7.8	—	23	—	—	9
6.	ω-[Co(en)(dien)Br] ²⁺	—	0.01 M, HClO ₄	—	—	—	—	—	4.4	7.0	13	22	—	45	9
7.	π-[Co(en)(dien)Cl] ²⁺	—	1.0 F, HClO ₄	1.0	—	—	—	—	5.2	8.7	—	—	—	—	12
8.	K ₂ [Co(en)(dien)Cl] ²⁺	—	1.0 F, HClO ₄	1.0	—	—	—	—	—	4.3	—	—	12.5	—	12
9.	ω-[Co(en)(dien)Cl] ²⁺	—	1.0 F, HClO ₄	1.0	—	—	—	—	—	3.7	—	—	11.2	—	12

Calculation of activation parameters :

The observed rate constants, K_{obs}, were calculated for each kinetic run from the first order equation :

$$k = \frac{2.303}{t} \log \frac{A_0 - A_t}{A_t - A_\infty}$$

where A₀ is the absorbance at reaction time zero, A_t is the absorbance at time t, and A_∞ is the absorbance at "infinity". This method was used for all pairs of successive points and the resulting ks were averaged.

In the graphical method, the rate constants were obtained from the slope of the plot of ln (A_t - A_∞) vs time.

The energies of activation, E_a, were calculated from a plot of ln k vs 1/T where slope = -E_a/R. log PZ values were then calculated from the Arrhenius equation :

$$\log k = \log PZ - E_a \times 1000 / (4.576 \times T)$$

The entropy of activation, ΔS[‡], was calculated from Wynne-Jones and Eyring equation :

$$k = \frac{RT}{Nh} e^{\Delta S^\ddagger / R} e^{-E_a / RT}$$

where N is Avogadro's number, R the gas constant and h the Planck's constant. By substituting the numerical values of constants in this equation, simplifying and taking logarithms, we get :

$$\log k = 10.319 + \log T + \frac{\Delta S^\ddagger}{4.576} - \frac{E_a}{4.576 \times T}$$

The formation equilibrium constant, K, for the adduct and the first order rate constant, k, for its dissociation were obtained from a plot of 1/k_{obs} against 1/[Mⁿ⁺] (Mⁿ⁺ = Ag⁺ or Hg₂²⁺). The expression for k_{obs} is given by k_{obs} = kK[Mⁿ⁺]/(1 + K[Mⁿ⁺]). Therefore 1/k_{obs} = (1/kK)(1/[Mⁿ⁺]) + 1/k. Thus, the slope = 1/kK ; k = 1/intercept and K = intercept/slope.

Results and Discussion

The spectrum of a solution initially containing [Co(en)(dien)X]²⁺ changes to that of [Co(en)(dien)H₂O]²⁺ in presence of excess silver nitrate or

mercurous nitrate. The kinetics were followed in dilute solutions of the complexes by measuring the change in absorbance at 520 nm for the chloro and at 540 nm for the bromo complexes. At these wave lengths, the two complexes absorb much more strongly than the aquo product. The assisted aquations were carried out at different Ag⁺ or Hg₂²⁺ ion concentrations, over a temp. range of 13-60°. The pH and the ionic strength was kept constant throughout. The initial complex concentration was chosen such that the initial absorbance ranged from 0.3 to 0.7 for a 1 cm path. To obtain pseudo first order kinetics, the initial [Ag⁺] or [Hg₂²⁺] was > 10 [complex].

The first order rate constants for the aquation of [Co(en)(dien)X]²⁺ are recorded in Table 1. A perusal of the Table indicates the temperature dependence of the rate constants. It is evident that the rate constants of the chloro and bromo complexes are almost equal in the temp. range of 40-60° and 65-80°, respectively. This may possibly be attributed to isomeric inter conversions which complicate the aquation of [Co(en)(dien)X]²⁺ system. The spectra of the solutions of the two complexes change regularly from 380 nm to 590 nm. The rest of the spectra are far less affected. The absorbances are somewhat higher at lower wave lengths where the parent complexes absorb much more strongly than the aquo products indicating that the reactions do not go to completion. The change in absorbance follows a first order rate law and the rate constants are independent of the wave length of measurements.

The catalysed aquations were conducted at different [Ag⁺] and [Hg₂²⁺] over a temp. range of 13-60° at constant pH and constant ionic strength. The pseudo first order rate constants for the Hg₂²⁺ ion assisted aquations of chloro and bromo complexes are given in Table 2.

It can be seen from Tables 1 and 2 that aquation of these two complexes is many times faster in the presence of metal ions. It is further found that the rates of Hg₂²⁺ ion catalysed aquation are faster (Table 2) than those catalysed by Ag⁺ ions (ref. 13). The differences in the rates of reactions are well borne out by various activation parameters which are given in Table 3.

TABLE 2—PSEUDO FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANTS FOR THE Hg_2^{2+} ION ASSISTED AQUATIONS OF $[Co(en)(dien)X]^{2+}$

[Complex] = $4.0 \times 10^{-3} M$; $[H^+] = 0.1 M$; $\mu = 1.0$ (KNO_3)

$[Hg_2^{2+}]$	$k_{obs} \times 10^4 \text{ sec}^{-1}$ at $^{\circ}C \pm 0.1^{\circ}$					
	Chloro complex			Bromo complex		
	20	30	40	13	20	25
0.10 M	7.0	12.5	33.3	12.8	22.1	28.4
0.15 M	12.6	25.6	46.6	18.6	28.6	36.8
0.20 M	27.3	52.1	70.0	32.5	43.3	55.7
0.30 M	52.0	85.8	106.6	57.8	71.1	91.4

TABLE 3—ACTIVATION RATE PARAMETERS FOR Ag^+ and Hg_2^{2+} ASSISTED AQUATION OF $[Co(en)(dien)X]^{2+}$ IN 0.1 M HNO_3

Complex	Assisting ion	$10^4 k_{obs} S^{-1}$	log PZ	E_a kcal mole $^{-1}$	ΔS^{\ddagger} cal deg $^{-1}$ mole $^{-1}$
$[Co(en)(dien)Cl]^{2+}$	Ag^+	7.5	5.92	13.7	-31
$[Co(en)(dien)Cl]^{2+}$	Hg_2^{2+}	12.9	4.62	11.6	-37
$[Co(en)(dien)Br]^{2+}$	Ag^+	45.2	4.87	11.2	-36
$[Co(en)(dien)Br]^{2+}$	Hg_2^{2+}	55.7	3.13	8.7	-44

It was found that both Ag^+ and Hg_2^{2+} catalysed aquation reactions have different activation energies at different temp. The activation energies between two temp. were calculated from the expression

$$E_a = \frac{RT_2 T_1}{T_2 - T_1} \ln \frac{k_2}{k_1}$$

The graphical values of E_a are given in Figs. 1-4. Comparing the activation energies of the Ag^+ and Hg_2^{2+} ion catalysed aquations, it is found that the latter have lower values and consequently more rapid rates. Coming to the nature of the leaving group, it is seen that the rates of bromo complex are higher than those of the chloro complex. Both Ag^+

and Hg_2^{2+} are class (b) acids and it is known that the usual overall stability order¹⁴ for class (b) metal ions is $Br > Cl$. It, therefore, seems reasonable to assume that Hg_2^{2+} ion is a better halide abstractor

Fig. 4

than Ag^+ ion. The assumption is further substantiated to some extent by considering the solubility product constants, K_{SP}^{15} , of silver and mercurous halides :

Metal halides	K_{SP}
AgCl	1.7×10^{-10}
AgBr	3.3×10^{-13}
Hg_2Cl_2	1.1×10^{-16}
Hg_2Br_2	1.3×10^{-21}

The lower K_{SP} values for mercurous halides may also be a contributing factor towards the enhanced rates of Hg_2^{2+} ion assisted aquations.

The entropy factor turns out to be another and possibly the dominant one in these reactions. A perusal of Table 3 indicates that these reactions proceed with a decrease in entropy. The negative entropies of activation indicates the fact that the activated complex will be a more highly charged ion which would be expected to be strongly solvated, so that more solvent molecules might be required than for the separate ions. The calculated values of the pre-exponential factor, PZ , (Table 3) of these reactions are found to be abnormally low. This condition is characteristic of reactions between ions of the same sign¹⁶.

The plots of $1/k_{obs}$ against $1/[\text{Ag}^+]$ and those of $1/k_{obs}$ against $1/[\text{Hg}_2^{2+}]$ for the chloro and bromo

complexes are all linear with finite positive intercepts (Figs. 5-8). The values of the formation equilibrium constants, K (M^{-1}) and the first order dissociation rate constants, k (sec^{-1}) of the activated complex are given in Table 4.

It can be seen from Table 4 that K increases slightly and k very little with increasing temperature.

In view of the above it is concluded that the Ag^+ and Hg_2^{2+} ion dependence can be summarized by $k_{obs} = kK[M^{n+}]/(1 + K[M^{n+}])$. The kinetics can be explained in terms of the formation of an adduct (activated complex) between the silver or mercurous

Fig. 5

Fig. 6

TABLE 4—FORMATION EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANTS AND FIRST ORDER DISSOCIATION RATE CONSTANTS OF THE ACTIVATED COMPLEX

 [Complex]=0.004 M ; [Ag⁺] or [Hg₂²⁺]=0.1 M, 0.15 M, 0.2 M, 0.3 M ; [H⁺]=0.1 M ; μ=1.0

Complex	Assisting ion		Temp. °C						
			18	20	25	30	40	50	60
[Co(en)(dien)Cl] ²⁺	Ag ⁺	K	—	—	—	—	2.24	2.88	3.4
		k × 10 ³	—	—	—	—	1.25	2.22	4.0
[Co(en)(dien)Cl] ²⁺	Hg ₂ ²⁺	K	—	1.71	—	1.90	2.20	—	—
		k × 10 ³	—	1.11	—	2.00	2.50	—	—
[Co(en)(dien)Br] ²⁺	Ag ⁺	K	—	—	—	—	2.34	3.57	3.68
		k × 10 ³	—	—	—	—	11.10	11.70	12.50
[Co(en)(dien)Br] ²⁺	Hg ₂ ²⁺	K	1.42	2.21	2.72	—	—	—	—
		k × 10 ³	1.05	1.17	1.25	—	—	—	—

Fig. 7

Fig. 8

ion such that $\frac{[\text{Activated complex}]}{[\text{Substrate}][\text{M}^{n+}]} = K$, ($\text{M}^{n+} = \text{Ag}^+$ or Hg_2^{2+}) and this is reflected in the change in the

spectrum of $[\text{Co(en)(dien)X}]^{2+}$ when silver nitrate or mercurous nitrate solution is added. The formation of the same aquo product $[\text{Co(en)(dien)H}_2\text{O}]^{2+}$ irrespective of the nature of the leaving group is explained on the basis of the spectral measurements. The spectral scanning of the product (at infinity) obtained in each reaction gave the same λ_{max} , no matter what the parent complex was. It appears that the reaction kinetics exhibit the characteristics of an $\text{S}_{\text{N}}1$ dissociative process. In the activated complex of the reaction, bond breaking is more important than bond making. The ¹H-nmr spectra of the chloro and bromo complexes suggest a structure in which the two ends of the diethylenetriamine are symmetrically sited. The activated complex appears to be a halogen bridged adduct which facilitates the breaking of the original metal halogen bond thereby favouring an essentially $\text{S}_{\text{N}}1$ type of substitution :

It is generally agreed¹⁷ that the separation of charge between cobalt and the departing ligand is more important than the neutralisation of charge between the entering water and the metal, but the latter is a necessary part of the overall act of substitution. We are currently examining these aquations in non-aqueous media and will discuss the problem in detail elsewhere.

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